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Analysis of Visual Representation Techniques for Product Configuration Systems in Industrial Companies

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Abstract – In recent years, there has been an increasing demand for customized products. Product configuration systems (PCS) are introduced as one of the most successful systems of artificial intelligent for providing customized products. One of the main challenges in PCSs projects are described in relation with knowledge representations and communications with domain experts. The results presented in the paper are therefore aimed to provide insight into the impact from using visual knowledge representations techniques in PCSs projects. The findings indicate that use of visual knowledge representations techniques in PCSs projects will result in improved quality of maintenance and development support for the knowledge base and improved quality of the communication with domain experts.

Keywords - Product configuration system (PCS), visual knowledge representation techniques, product modelling

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive environment, companies are pressured to offer customized solutions without compromising delivery time, quality and cost [1]. Mass customization refers to the ability to make customized products and services, which fit individual customers [2]. Product configuration systems (PCSs) have been defined as one of the main success factor to achieve the benefits from the mass customization approach [2]. PCS have a knowledge-integrated or intelligent product model, which means that it contains the knowledge about the company's products range.

Knowledge representations techniques are concerned with formalizing the product architecture in a way that allows the designer or product developer to elaborate, evaluate and communicate [3]. Knowledge representations technique is a high level concept for all types of modeling created in relation to product development or for communication regarding the product assortment [4]. Tomiyama [5] defines that "Modelling is a process in which observed facts are filtered by a theory".

In PCSs projects there is a need for modelling the products and transforming that model into an information model that can be used for programming of the actual system. A phenomenon model represents the product model and the information model represents a model that can be implemented in the software. A phenomenon model is a model of real world, which corresponds to a product model and used to communicate with non-IT people. Next, the phenomenon model is formalized into

an information model to be incorporated into an IT-system [6]. The information model can be communicated across the IT teams while the phenomenon model can be used for all stakeholders. The process from representing information based on the "real world" until a computer model has been constructed is demonstrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. From Real world to the IT-system [6]

As a result, to the information model to be based on IT representations, which is not understandable to most domain experts or not the most efficient way for communications, the phenomenon model helps domain experts and IT experts to communicate in a common language. The phenomenon model equals the visual knowledge representation used for communication with domain experts.

The impact from applying visual knowledge representations techniques in PCSs projects, in terms of quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support and for communications with domain experts has not been addressed in previous studies. This research aims to capture this opportunity by analyzing the experiences from using the visual knowledge representations in PCSs projects. The focus of the research is not to study the quality of different techniques for knowledge representations but focus on assessing the impact from applying these techniques. The following propositions have been developed aligned with the research focus.

Proposition 1. The higher the degree of visual knowledge representations, the higher the quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support.

Proposition 2. The higher the degree of visual knowledge representations, the higher the quality of communication with experts.

In order to analyze the propositions, a survey is under design. In this paper, the preliminary results from the research will be presented, which are based on structured interviews in six engineer-to-order (ETO) companies. The results support the developed propositions, as positive impact is found from using visual knowledge representations techniques on the quality of development and maintenance support of the knowledge base and in communications with domain experts.

The structure of the paper is as following. In the second chapter of this paper an explanation of the research method is given. In the third chapter the relevant literature is introduced. In the fourth chapter the results of the research are presented. Finally, in fifth chapter, conclusion and further research are elaborated.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The results presented in this research are part of a larger survey, which is under development. The results presented in this paper are however based on structured interviews carried out into six ETO companies working with PCSs. The aim is to capture specifics reasoning and information relevant to the particular companies. The companies represent small, medium and large companies, where the level of customization and the complexity of the offered products varies greatly. The criteria for the selected companies were based on ETO manufacturing companies using PCSs to support sales and engineering processes. Based on the hypothesis, the following questions were asked to the interviewees:

Q.1) To what extent do you apply visual modelling techniques in configuration projects? (Modelling techniques are UML, Product Variant Master (PVM), Feature Models, Other) [1...10] (Not at all...To great extent)

Q.2) Assess the quality of knowledge base development and maintenance support? [1...10] (Very low...Very high)

Q.3) To which extent are these modelling techniques helpful when it comes to communicate with domain experts? [1...10] (Not helpful...Very helpful, N/A)

The companies were asked on the scale 1-10 to what extent visual representations are used in PCS projects, where 1 represent that visual knowledge representations are not being used and 10 represents that visual knowledge representations are being used to a great extent. Furthermore, the companies were asked to rate on the scale 1-10, the quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support and the quality in communication with domain experts. In each company there was only one person responsible for answering the survey and the contact the persons were selected based on familiarity with the configurators irrespective of their formal role at the company.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section provides the theoretical background for the study, which includes techniques for knowledge representations. The different knowledge representations techniques are categorized according to whether they support visual knowledge representation, empirical findings in terms of case study and the targeted group that the technique is aimed for (configuration engineers or domain experts). The main findings from the literature study are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

LITERATURE AVAILABLE ON PRODUCT MODELING (KNOWLEDGE REPRESENTING) IN PCS

	Knowledge representation techniques	Case study	Target group	
			Domain experts	Configuration Engineers (IT experts)
Available research on knowledge representation	Visual	Industrial application		
Andreasen [7]	x		x	
Aldanondo et al. [8]	x			x
Soininen et al. [9]	x			x
Haug et al. [10]	x	x	x	x
Felfernig et al. [11]	x	x	x	x
Nagel et al. [12]	x	x		x
Mortensen et al. [13]	x	x	x	x
Dahmus et al. [14]	x	x	x	
Chao et al. [15]				x
Magro et al. [16]	x	x		x
Tseng et al. [17]	x	x		x
Jinsong et al. [18]	x	x		x
Yang et al. [19]				x
Zhang et al. [20]		x		x
Zhang et al. [21]		x		x
Mailharro [22]		x		x
Stumptner et al. [23]	x		x	
Felfernig [24]	x	x		x
Hvam et al. [25]	x			x
Haug et al. [26]	x	x	x	x
Erens et al. [27]	x	x	x	x
Felfernig et al. [28]	x	x		x
Felfernig et al. [29]	x	x	x	x
McGuinness et al. [30]	x		x	
Felfernig et al. [31]				x

Product modelling represents a formal expression of the products or product families' structure and the knowledge. One of the main requirements for the applicability of standard knowledge representations is a graphical or visual knowledge representation, which makes it possible to improve the communication between domain experts and configuration engineers [32]. Sabin et al. [33] introduces the knowledge gathering and representation as one of the most challenging parts in PCS projects. Felfernig [24] emphasizes the importance of the standard knowledge representation in configuration projects for the effective integration of configuration technologies into software environment dealing with highly engineered complex products. The visual knowledge representation is usually helpful for the communication between domain expert and configuration engineer as well as documentation and maintenance of the PCS model.

There are multiple suggested techniques in order to fulfil the knowledge representation task. Commonly applied techniques in PCS projects are [34]: Product

variant master (PVM) associated with class diagrams and CRC-cards mainly inspired by Unified Modelling Language (UML) [10, 11, 35, 36]. These techniques support both the visual and the conceptual modelling of the products as well as communication and documentation. Another commonly used technique is the object-oriented modelling technique, which is also based on UML; this technique can be used independent from the type of software and can also be used for the systems' documentation [35]. Mortensen et al. [13] present a Product Family Master Plan (PFMP) for visualizing the product assortment and shows the practicality of the technique and its benefits for simplifying the communication process between domain experts and configuration engineers [13]. Erens et al. [27] conclude that the development of a product family requires product architectures in three domains, the required function, technological realization and the physical realization. In this research a case study is provided, which highlights the benefits for all the stakeholders at the company due to the technique utilization [27]. Haug et al. [10] integrate different knowledge representation techniques in a documentation system and use IT support from the Lotus Note application in the maintenance phase of the PCS model. In this research, the documentation system is tested in industrial application where it proves its usability [10]. Tseng et al. [17] study the Case-Based Reasoning (CBR) algorithm to help in the process of generating a right BOM and visualize their model in a tree structure. Zhang et al. [21] analyze the development and modelling of a PCS, which is not a visualization technique, and they provide an illustrated example based on a case to prove their concept. Mailharro et al. [22] combines concepts based on object-oriented paradigms but do not use any visualization. They introduce a structured framework for knowledge representation in PCSs projects as an information model for the IT team or the configuration engineers. Dahmus et al. [14] use a matrix of functions versus products, which shared function levels are indicated; the approach aimed to analyze modules for the Black and Decker VersaPak portfolio of products.

Most of the researchers provide evidences from industry to prove the advantages of using visual knowledge representation techniques. Hvam et al. [10] present a case from industry where the proposed software developed and the authors support all the discussion by providing examples step by step. Mortensen et al. [13] test the idea of PFMP for one of Baan's (SSA Global) customers with very convincing results and supportive discussions.

Communication can be described as a way to manage relationships between producers and consumers [37]. Communication is an important factor in software development and, thus, a relatively common success factor, when discussing change in software development projects and teams [38]. Tseng et al. [17] describe that a common problem in configuration project is the lack of communication with domain experts as it is easy to lose control of the product configuration due to the incomplete

communication or configurations conflicts, if the company is dependent on the knowledge or experience of the employees.

IV. RESULTS

In this chapter the main results from the research are presented. The results are based on answers gathered from structured interviews in six ETO companies. The results represent the impact of using visual knowledge representation techniques on the quality of the PCS's knowledge base development and maintenance support and the quality of communications with domain experts. In the following sections the impact from using knowledge representations will be elaborated aligned with the propositions developed for the research.

A. The impact from using visual knowledge representations on the knowledge base development and maintenance support

In this section the results will be elaborated in terms of use of visual knowledge representations and the quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The results based on the interviews (Axe Y: Rated impact, Axe X: Company ID)

In three of the case companies (companies 1, 5 and 6), visual knowledge representations are being used to a great extent or on the scale of 8-10. In those cases, it can also be identified that the quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support is rated excellent or on the scale of 8-9. This indicates that companies using visual knowledge representations in PCSs projects have high quality of knowledge base development and maintenance support.

In case 4, the use of visual knowledge representations is rated 6 and the quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support is rated good, or on the scale 7. In case 2, the use of visual knowledge representations is rated 3 and the quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support is rated as fairly good, or on the scale 4. This indicates that there is a correlation between the use visual knowledge representations and development in PCSs projects.

In case 3, the use of visual knowledge representations is rated 5 and the quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support is rated excellent,

or on the scale 9. This is not aligned with the results from the other cases as it seems to be no correlation between the uses of visual knowledge representations and the quality of the knowledge base development and maintenance support.

From the above analysis can be concluded that when the rate of using visual knowledge representation techniques is greater than 5, the support and development capabilities are higher than average.

B. The impact from using visual knowledge representations in communications with domain experts

In this section, the results will be elaborated in terms of use of visual knowledge representations and the quality of communications with domain experts as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The results based on the interviews (Axe Y: Rated impact, Axe X: Company ID)

In three of the case companies (companies 1, 5 and 6), visual knowledge representations are being used to great extent or on the scale of 9-10. In those cases, it can also be identified that the quality of the communications with domain experts is rated excellent or on the scale of 8-9. This indicates that companies using visual knowledge representations in PCSs projects have high quality of communication with domain experts.

In case 4, the use of visual knowledge representations is rated 6 and the quality of communication is rated good, or on the scale 6. In case 2, the use of visual knowledge representations is rated 3 and the quality of communication is rated medium, or on the scale 5. This indicates that companies using visual knowledge representations in PCSs projects benefiting from the perceived quality in communications with domain experts.

In case 3, the use of visual knowledge representation techniques is rated as 5 and the quality in communications with domain experts is rated 5 or medium as well. This can be interpreted that there is a great correlation between the constructs.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The results presented in this article are based on structured interviews in six ETO companies contacted to analyse the impact from using visual knowledge

representation techniques in PCS projects. The result indicates that companies using visual knowledge representation techniques, tend to have higher quality of the PCS's knowledge base development and maintenance support and to have higher quality with regards to communications with domain experts. As by using visual knowledge representations, it gives the configuration team a better understanding of products and expected outputs. Furthermore, companies using visual knowledge representations techniques to less extent tend to have greater problems in communications with domain experts. Based on the interviews, while considering the type of the projects, size and complexity it seems that the more complicated and the larger the project is the influence and gains from applying visual knowledge representation methods on the road is higher. Finally, with regards to maintenance and considering the types of projects, it seems that any knowledge representation method will lead to better communication, which will lead to the higher quality in validation and maintenance of the PCSs. On the other hand and based on the survey, the companies which are gaining benefits from IT software to automate the visual knowledge representation process, rated for a higher communication level and easier maintenance.

The results of this research are based on the limited number of companies; therefore, significant result cannot be stated. Nevertheless, the results are thought to provide a useful insight that highlights the benefits from using visual knowledge representations techniques in PCSs projects. These results were gathered as preliminary result for larger survey that is under development.

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